

Rac-1ag

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-100-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0901
Vial:	31	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 100 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	13.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/31/2021 10:52:33 PM CST		
Date Processed:	9/1/2021 8:41:57 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.354	5889394	51.15	643621
2	10.060	5624535	48.85	455979

Asy-1ag

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-113-1-S-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0901
Vial:	32	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 113 1 S
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	13.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/31/2021 11:11:23 PM CST		
Date Processed:	9/1/2021 8:43:23 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.368	535608	2.93	56365
2	10.035	17759957	97.07	1411623